

Deep Learning Approach to Improve Spatial Resolution of GOES-R Satellite Imagery for Active Fire Detection Using VIIRS Satellite Data

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Wildfires are increasingly frequent and destructive worldwide [1], posing severe risks to ecosystems [2-5], infrastructure [6-10], and public safety [11-13]. As global warming exacerbates these risks, highlighting the urgent need for advanced active wildfire detection models to support timely response and damage mitigation. Current active wildfire (AF) detection products, such as NOAA's Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite-R series (GOES-R) AF product [14], and NASA's MCD14DL [15] and VNP14IMGTDL_NRT [16, 17] based on Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) and Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) imagery, respectively, enable large-scale monitoring of wildfire occurrences. However, these products are constrained by threshold-based methods, and outdated statistical or physical models, limiting their accuracy and generalizability across diverse geographical regions and fire conditions [18, 19]. In addition, existing active fire products face spatial-temporal trade-offs: GOES-R AF product provides high temporal (5 min for the Continental United States (CONUS)–15 min for the Western Hemisphere/full disk) but low spatial resolution (2 km), resulting in missed detections of small or low-intensity fires, overestimation of fire size, and a high false alarm rate. In contrast, MODIS and VIIRS AF products offer finer spatial resolution (500 m, 375 m) but a 12-hour revisit time, resulting in significant temporal gaps that restrict real-time applications.

In response, this study proposes a two-step framework: (1) super-resolution (SR) of GOES-R data to approximate VIIRS-level detail, and (2) application of a transformer based deep learning (DL) model to detect active fires in super-resolved images. The approach exploits the complementary spatial and temporal strengths of both sensors, enabling detection of small, low-intensity, and fast-spreading fires often missed by threshold-based methods. While DL methods have been used separately for SR enhancement and active fire detection with MODIS [20] and VIIRS [21] imagery, limited studies have integrated both for near-real-time detection with GOES-R data.

Our super-resolution model follows a modern encoder–decoder autoencoder (AE; Figure 1d) with skip connections and transformer-style attention blocks that performs multi-scale upsampling on a co-registered GOES-R crop over the VIIRS footprint. The AE maps low-resolution GOES-R ABI image to a VIIRS-like, high-resolution data for downstream active-fire detection. Training uses near-coincident GOES-R and VIIRS event pairs for pixel-wise correspondence, with a physics-aware loss that enforces radiometric fidelity, structural preservation, downsample-consistency back to GOES-R scale, and hotspot-aware weighting for fire lines and active cores. The super-resolved output, together with an uncertainty channel and the original GOES-R context, is then fed to a lightweight transformer-based segmentation model to produce per-pixel fire probabilities and crisp boundaries.

Preliminary results indicate that the proposed AE-based SR model effectively sharpens and localizes the hotspot toward the VIIRS peak while suppressing background fluctuations (Figure 1c). In addition, the predicted fire mask (Figure 1e) exhibits cleaner and more compact detections from the super-resolved GOES-R imagery compared with the GOES-R derived baseline, supporting GIS-ready polygon extraction. This study demonstrates the feasibility of super-resolved GOES-R imagery for real-world active fire detection, offering practical contributions to early warning systems that support emergency response and resource allocation.

Figure 1. Downscale GOES-R thermal band 7 (a) to approximate VIIRS thermal band I4 (b) for active fire detection with an autoencoder architecture (d); The model sharpens and localizes the hotspot toward the VIIRS peak (c) while suppressing background fluctuations; The predicted fire mask (e right) row demonstrates cleaner, more compact detections from the model output compared with a GOES-derived baseline (e left).

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